

Collegial Interaction and Conversational Skills Among English Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract. The researcher aimed to determine the association between collegial interaction and conversational skills among English secondary school teachers by using descriptive correlation of research with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistical tools—multiple linear regression analysis. Moreover, the researcher selected 189 English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary public schools in Davao City as the study’s respondents. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers was extensive, while conversation skills among English secondary school teachers were moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between collegial interaction and conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 public secondary schools in Davao City. Regression analysis proved that collegial interaction regarding justice, fairness, good faith, and trust significantly influenced conversation skills among English secondary school teachers. In other words, collegial interaction influences the conversation skills process among English secondary school teachers. The study, therefore, was conducted to further utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching English 2. collegial interaction 3. conversation skills

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1. Introduction

This collegial discussion enables teachers to share their practice as a means of improving their own knowledge about teaching and learning in their learning area. Research about learning or education has generally been applicable to teaching and learning development. Collegial discussion is built on mutual respect and trust. For it to become a meaningful professional conversation, the teachers should be actively listening and providing honest feedback. Similarly, Good conversational skills are not only needed for the effective teaching profession, but it is also very important for the effectiveness of every concern of one’s life. Conversational skills, as described by Khan et al. (2017), are the ability to transmit a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place. Educa-

tor with good conversational skills always make the things easier and understandable. With good conversation skills, educators could easily facilitate learning in accordance with the ability and capability of the students which motivate the students toward their learning processes (Sng Bee, 2012). Likewise, Nanthaboot (2012) asserted that with effective conversational activities encourage individuals to use language in appropriate situations and social interactions because it makes an individual notice who is talking with whom, when they should or should not say something, and how they should say something. In short, effective conversational skills is essential for effective learning processes and social interaction relating to individuals' life concerns. However, Alsubaie (2017) highlighted that poor conversational skills among educators at different levels remain an increasing problem, especially in language education. For instance, the report of Yusof and Halim (2014) showed that poor conversational and communication ability of language teachers adversely affects their productivity, efficiency, and effectiveness because the productivity of English language educators depends on their ability to develop students' communication competence. Also, Okoli (2017) reported that teachers' poor conversational skills result in a twenty percent decrease in students' attendance. Similarly, Akiri (2013) has observed that teachers' ineffectiveness in conversation and communication activities results in poor performance of the students not only in language class but also in other disciplines such as mathematics and sciences. This is because, as noted by Phin (2014), a teacher who does not possess conversational ability and communicative competence to impart is less approachable and is not attentive to students' needs. Various authors reported positive link between collegial interaction on conversational skills of educators. For instance, Cakir (2010) and Wardhaugh (2011) asserted that cultural competence influence conversational skills in line with the view that culture is patterned behavior, where language is a vital component of the culture. Accordingly, individuals conduct their social lives with language and when language is used in context of communication, it is bound up with culture in various and complex ways. On the other hand, the study of Crawford (2010) linked quality organizational relationships in terms of fairness to conversational skills among working individuals. The study emphasized that showing fairness engages employees to become responsible for the service encounter, thereby creating an environment where individuals are emotionally invested by expressing thoughts during conversation events. Hence, the stated literature validates the claim of the current study of the positive link between cultural competence and organizational relationships on conversational skills. The context of the above-mentioned studies was in foreign settings and among educators at college levels. Therefore, to fill in the gap, in this study, the teachers' talk and conversational medium communication skills are viewed within the contexts in which and how they are used and as contributing to the integration of teachers' language as conversational skills. For this study, several features of conversational skills, including attentiveness and coordination, vocalics and composure, and expressiveness, will be explored. This was conducted in the Philippine setting, particularly among the public secondary schools using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher utilized descriptive-correlational design to have a better understanding of the English teachers' conversational skills as determined by collegial interaction which is found to be scarce. The results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as it could provide valuable knowledge to their research. Adding more, the result of this study may provide quantitative inputs that are research-based in crafting an enhancement plan regarding the conversational skills of the teachers

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative research, as described by Bhandari (2020), stresses a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacked the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher looked into the relationship between two variables— collegial interaction and the conversational skills of the teachers. In this connection, the study focused on exploring which domains of collegial interaction significantly influence the conversational skills of the teachers. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the public English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 Schools in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City. In this study, 189 respondents were selected through a stratified random

sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular public secondary English teachers in Cluster 6 Schools, Davao City, who voluntarily signed the ICF, were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administering the instrument, it was subjected to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments. The first part of the instrument focused on the collegial interaction of the public secondary school teachers. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Potgieter et al. (2015). Collegial interaction is

indicated with justice, fairness, good faith, and trust. The modified questionnaire obtained a Cronbach alpha value of 0.716, interpreted as good and acceptable. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert

scale. As a guide in determining the extent of collegial interaction, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The collegial interaction is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The collegial interaction is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The collegial interaction is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The collegial interaction is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The collegial interaction is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was about the conversational skills of the public secondary school teachers. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Winger (2017) and indicated attentiveness and coordination, vocalists and composure, and expressiveness. The modified questionnaire obtained a Cronbach alpha value

of 0.977, interpreted as excellent. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use of the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of conversational skills, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean Descriptive Levels and Interpretations

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The conversational skills are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The conversational skills are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The conversational skills are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The conversational skills are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The conversational skills are never manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research question-

naire. 1. *Permission to Conduct the Study.* The researcher secured permission to conduct the study and the endorsement from the Dean of

the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City's endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City. To obtain permission to conduct the study from the selected secondary public schools in Cluster 5 in Davao City, the researchers personally brought the letters to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher initially appeared in the principal's office last February 2023 to carry the letters asking permission to conduct the study. The principals accepted the letters. However, the principals reminded the researcher that the Division Superintendent's protocols should be strictly followed during the study. This includes the lack of disruption of classes and the health protocols con-

cerning the COVID-19 crisis. After this, the researcher proceeded to distribute and retrieve the survey questionnaires. 2. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the study was approved, the researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents. The study was conducted to administer the questionnaire in the fourth quarter of the school year 2022-2023. Moreover, the study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. 3. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire data was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' collegial interaction and conversational skills. It was also used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (collegial in-

teraction) and dependent (conversational skills) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by r . Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to evaluate the significance of which domains of the independent (collegial interaction) variable significantly influence the dependent (conversational skills) variable.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It was sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of collegial interactions and conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City; the significant relationship between collegial interactions and conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City; and the domains of collegial interactions that significantly influence the conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City.

Summary of Collegial Interaction among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Table 1 summarizes the extent of collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in

Davao City. The table shows that collegial interaction obtained an overall mean score of 3.41, descriptively rated as extensive and interpreted as often observed. Also, the table denotes that collegial interaction in terms of good faith acquired the highest mean score of 3.48, described

as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, collegial interaction in terms of fairness acquired the lowest mean score of 3.32, which is described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed.

Table 1. Summary of Collegial Interaction among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Justice	3.46	Extensive
Fairness	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Good Faith	3.48	Extensive
Trust	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.41	Extensive

This denotes that sharing insights, strategies, resources, and experiences related to teaching English at the secondary school level is oftentimes observed in Cluster 5 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The result agrees with Oluchi's (2013) argument that collegial interaction fosters continuous professional growth. Teachers can learn from each other's experiences, expertise, and innovative approaches, improving teaching practices at the high school level. The result agrees with De la Rosa Navarro and Cabrera's (2009) assertion that teachers can collaboratively explore and adopt effective pedagogical strategies through collegial interactions. Sharing best practices and discussing instructional methods can produce a richer repertoire of teaching strategies for high school English educators.

Summary Table on the Extent of Conversa-

The study's findings imply that the extent of the ability to transmit a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication occurs is sometimes manifested among English sec-

tional Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Table 2 summarizes the extent of conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City. The overall mean of the conversational skills among English secondary school teachers is 3.39, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. More, conversational skills in terms of vocalics and composure acquired the highest mean score of 3.48, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. In contrast, conversational skills in terms of attentiveness and coordination, acquired the lowest mean score of 3.32, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City.

ondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. This result coincides with the idea of Ahmed (2018) that conversational skills are both the knowledge of the linguistic and non-linguistic rules of communication and the skill

Table 2. Summary Table on the Extent of Conversational Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Attentiveness and Coordination	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Vocalics and Composures	3.48	Extensive
Expressiveness	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

to use such knowledge effectively and appropriately in real-life situations to fulfill communicative goals. Likewise, the result coincides with Nanthaboot's (2012) assertion that conversational activities include any tasks that encourage and require an individual to speak with and listen to another individual and with people in the community.

Relationship Between Collegial Interaction and Conversational Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City

The results of the analysis of the relationship between collegial interaction and conversational skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that collegial interaction has a significant positive relationship with the conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 secondary schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .921, p < 0.05$). This means that as the extent of the collegial interaction changes, the level of conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5

secondary schools in Davao City also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that collegial interaction in terms of justice, fairness, good faith, and trust is significantly correlated with conversational skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City, as evident from the correlation coefficient values of 0.829, 0.899, 0.662, and 0.656. This leads to rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between collegial interaction and conversational skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City. This implies that the collaborative and professional exchanges within a collegial environment create opportunities for teachers to enhance their communication abilities. The result agrees with Adegbuyi et al. (2015) claim that collegial interaction provides English teachers with opportunities to observe and model effective communication skills. Through conversations with colleagues, they can witness exemplary communication practices, including active listening, clarity, and empathy, which they can incorporate into their conversational skills. Teachers engaging in collegial interactions often share their experiences and best practices. This exchange of insights includes effective communication strategies employed in the classroom.

Domains of Collegial Interaction that Significantly Influence the Conversation Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster

5 Schools, Davao City

The significance of the influence of collegial interaction on the conversational skills among

Table 3. Relationship Between Collegial Interaction and Conversational Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Collegial Interaction	r-value	p-value	Decision
Justice	0.829*	0.000	Reject H0
Fairness	0.899*	0.000	Reject H0
Good Faith	0.662*	0.000	Reject H0
Trust	0.656*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Collegial Interaction	0.921*	0.000	Reject H0

**Significant at p<0.05*

English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. Table 4 shows that when collegial interaction in terms of justice, fairness, good faith, and trust are considered predictors of conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City, the model is significant, as evident in the F-value of 20.377 with $p<0.05$. Therefore, collegial interaction predicts

the conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.327 indicates that collegial interaction has contributed significantly in the variability of conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City by 32.70 from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 67.30 was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

Table 4. Domains of Collegial Interaction that Significantly Influence the Conversation Skills among English Secondary School Teachers in Cluster 5 Schools, Davao City

Collegial Interaction	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decision
Justice	0.391*	0.327	0.078	0.000	Reject H0
Fairness	0.151*	0.139	0.070	0.033	Reject H0
Good Faith	0.124*	0.134	0.062	0.040	Reject H0
Trust	0.232*	0.226	0.063	0.000	Reject H0
R ²	0.327				
F-value	20.377**				
p-value	0.000				

**Significant at p<0.05, **Significant at p<0.01*

In addition, the table shows that there are domains of collegial interaction that significantly influence the conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5

schools in Davao City. This table indicates that collegial interaction in terms of justice, fairness, good faith, and trust are significant predictors of conversational skills among English secondary

school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. This means that the extent of classroom behavior increases by 0.391, 0.151, 0.124, and 0.232 for each unit increase in collegial. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of collegial interaction significantly influence conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. Affirming that conversation skills for in English secondary school teachers is a function of collegial interaction, the finding agrees with the view of Banihashemi (2011) that collegial interactions create a supportive environment for teachers to give

and receive constructive feedback. Engaging in reflective discussions with peers helps teachers identify areas for improvement in their conversational skills. Constructive feedback allows for targeted development and refinement of communication techniques. Lastly, the findings is in agreement with the anchored proposition by Kaur (2013) that collegial interactions provide a platform for language support and development. Through discussions with peers, English teachers can receive feedback on language usage, expand their vocabulary, and refine their linguistic skills, enhancing their overall conversational proficiency.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion was supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion was by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of collegial interaction significantly influence conversational skills among English secondary school teachers. This was done by utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-predictive technique. The researcher selected 189 English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 public secondary schools in Davao City as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: Collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City has an overall mean of 3.41 with a descriptive rating of extensive. Meanwhile, collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers regarding justice, fairness, good faith, and trust obtained

mean scores of 3.46, 3.32, 3.48, and 3.36, respectively. Conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City have an overall mean of 3.39 and a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Also, conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in terms of attentiveness and coordination, vocalists and composure, and expressiveness obtained mean scores of 3.32, 3.48, and 3.36, respectively. The result showed that collegial interaction has a significant positive relationship with the conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .921$, $p < 0.05$). Overall, collegial interaction significantly influences the conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City, as evidenced by the F-value of 117.884 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.638 indicated that collegial interaction had contributed significantly to the variability of conversation skills among English

secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City by 32.70 from the total variability. Moreover, collegial interaction in terms of justice, fairness, good faith, and trust was found to be a significant predictor of conversation skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City, as indicated by the regression coefficient values of 0.391, 0.151, 0.124 and 0.232, respectively.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City was rated as extensive. Collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers in terms of justice and good faith was rated as extensive, while collegial interaction among English secondary school teachers in terms of fairness and trust was rated as moderately extensive. This means that the extent to which employees, immediate supervisors, and other parties in the relationship experience interactions, exchanges, and various mediators associated with a working relationship as positive or negative are oftentimes observed among English secondary school teachers in Cluster 5 public secondary schools in Davao City. Conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 Davao City schools were rated moderately extensive. Conversational skills among English secondary school teachers regarding vocalists and composure were rated as extensive. In contrast, conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in terms of attentiveness, coordination, and expressiveness were rated as moderately extensive. This implies that the extent of the ability to transmit a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place is sometimes manifested. The result showed that collegial interaction has a significant positive relationship with conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. As

the extent of the collegial interaction changes, conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City also significantly change. This implies that the collaborative and professional exchanges within a collegial environment create opportunities for teachers to enhance their communication abilities. The extent of collegial interaction in terms of justice, fairness, good faith, and trust significantly influenced the conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of collegial interaction significantly influence the conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The researcher may recommend lecturing teachers on teachers' involvement in educational decisions such as financial issues, choosing teachers, determining programs, and measuring student success. This is because when teachers participate in making decisions, their problem-solving ability improves, and the entire school benefits from it, resulting in a feeling of stronger commitment to the overall organization. However, school heads may have certain and well-explained rules regarding teacher participation to avoid becoming a privilege for just a few teachers. School heads may try to enhance employees' perceived organizational justice to improve their perception of organizational justice because if employees are not treated fairly, it results in reduced output from the employees as a natural response to the unfair treatment. School heads must consider when they formulate and implement justice strategies to influence teachers' attitudes and behaviors. They may ensure both processes are fair, transparent, and just and distributions are equitable and reasonable distributions. Furthermore, the study

found that collegial interaction only contributed to 32.70 of the total variability of conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City. Thus, the researcher recommends that other researchers should conduct an explanatory study on the mediating factors that causes the relationship between collegial interaction and conversational skills among English secondary school teachers in cluster 5 schools in Davao City in a larger context may be conducted.

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